

1 Interoception moderates the relation between alexithymia and risky-choices in a
2 framing task: a proposal of two-stage model of decision-making

3

4 **ABSTRACT**

5 Decision-making depends on the context (frame) in which questions and alternatives are
6 presented. Moreover, research has showed that the ability to detect bodily sensations
7 (interoception) and being able to attribute these changes to emotions correctly (alexithymia)
8 influence how we make decisions. The aim of the present research was to study how
9 interoception and alexithymia might affect the Framing effect (FE), a cognitive bias closely
10 related to emotional system. 42 healthy participants completed the Risky-choice Framing task
11 and their interoception and alexithymia levels were measured. Results showed that the
12 participants were more risk-taking under the negative frames in comparison to the positive
13 ones. In addition, we found that alexithymia and interoception were negatively and positively
14 correlated with the FE, respectively. Finally, the moderation analyses revealed that
15 alexithymia predicted a lower FE only when the interoception was high. Based on previous
16 literature and in our results, we propose a two-stage model of intuitive decision-making.

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18 **Key words:** decision-making, framing effect, interoception, alexithymia, somatic markers,
19 emotions

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1. INTRODUCTION

Our day-to-day decisions are characterized by violation of rationality premises. In daily life ambiguous situations and due to our cognitive and time limitations, instead of analyzing the whole problem and calculating all the possible outcomes, we rely on our “gut feelings” or constantly let our emotions dictate our decisions (Bechara & Damasio, 2005; De Martino, Harrison, Knafo, Bird, & Dolan, 2008; Kahneman & Tversky, 1979; Poppa & Bechara, 2017). Therefore, we tend to take cognitive “shortcuts”, known as *heuristics*. These heuristics can lead to biases and systematic errors (Kahneman, & Tversky, 1979). One of the most studied biases is the “**Framing effect**” (FE).

FE, one of the main pillars of the Prospect theory (Kahneman, & Tversky, 1979), contradicts the main premise of the rational choice theory (Mellers, Schwartz, & Cooke, 1998): logical consistency across decisions, regardless of the context. This bias consists of the idea that changes in the context, it means, changes in the way alternatives are presented, affect relative desirability of these alternatives, in the way that people tend to prefer the sure option in the positive frame and the risky option in the negative frame (Tversky & Kahneman, 1981). In other words, choices involving gains make people more risk averse and choices involving losses, more risk taking. This bias has also been observed in animal studies (see Kacelnik & Bateson, 1996, 1997 for review) and seems to have its roots in emotional system since studies have observed that prefrontal-amygdala circuit (De Martino, Kumaran, Seymour, & Dolan, 2006; Roiser et al., 2009) and insular cortex (Preuschoff, Quartz, & Bossaerts, 2008) play an important role in this process. Different studies have shown that these brain circuits are involved in emotions processing (e.g. Bechara, Damasio, Damasio, & Anderson, 1994; Chakravarthy & Chakravarthy, 2019; Craig, 2009; Ledoux, 2000; Phelps, 2006; Poppa & Bechara, 2017; Trepel, Fox, & Poldrack, 2005). For instance, several lines of research, working with patients with brain damage in this circuit, support the idea that this leads to

1 excess risk-taking without anticipating the negative costs that this may entail (Bechara &
2 Damasio, 2005; De Martino, Camerer, & Adolphs, 2010; Phelps, 2006) and it is believed that
3 this is because of their inability to detect emotional body cues triggered by aversive stimuli
4 (Bechara et al., 1994). Other studies (De Martino et al., 2008; Ring, 2015; Sarlo, Lotto,
5 Palomba, Scozzari, & Rumiati, 2013) using more peripheral indicators of emotional arousal,
6 such as skin conductance responses (SCRs), observed a differential physiological pattern
7 depending on how the problems and the possible alternatives were presented: higher SCRs
8 being positively correlated with negative frames and also with high risk-taking under this
9 context. Put in another way, a higher arousal was linked to a higher FE. Thus, these findings,
10 on central and peripheral nervous system level, show that emotions play an essential role in
11 this process, it means, how a certain situation makes us feel or how we “label” those feelings
12 can alter our perspective and affect our decisions.

13 Talking about the role of emotions in our decision-making, De Martino et al. (2006)
14 highlighted that studies with the FE emphasize the fact that intuition and emotional responses,
15 instead of analytical processing, play a key role in guiding choice behavior. Though, more
16 research is needed to get a deeper perspective of the situation; nevertheless, this limited data
17 still manages to make it obvious that emotions are an indispensable part of human decision-
18 making process, as well as, how we process and regulate them. However, this would be
19 highly depending on the individual’s emotional awareness level; in fact, it has been shown
20 that higher emotional awareness is linked to a better performance in complex decision-making
21 tasks (Evans, Bowman, & Turnbull, 2005). For this reason, it would be interesting to consider
22 the role the constructs involving these variables, such as alexithymia and interoception.

23 **Alexithymia**, first introduced by Sifneos (1973), with a 10-13% prevalence rate in
24 general population depending on the cutoff we use (Salminen, Saarijärvi, Äärelä, Toikka, &
25 Kauhanen, 1999), is a personality construct which consists in having difficulties in identifying

1 and describing one's emotions and feelings. These symptoms can result in having trouble in
2 emotional regulation and awareness (da Silva, Vasco, & Watson, 2017; Hsing, Mohr,
3 Stansfield, & Preston, 2013; Laloyaux, Fantini, Lemaire, Luminet, & Larøi, 2015; Zamariola,
4 Vlemincx, Luminet, & Corneille, 2018) and deficits in the perception of emotional stimuli
5 (Aleman, 2005; Lane, Sechrest, Riedel, Shapiro, & Kaszniak, 2000). Working with the FE,
6 Shah, Hall, Catmur, & Bird (2016) demonstrated that higher levels of alexithymia predicted
7 lower FE, concluding that individuals with alexithymia tend to rely more on "rationality" than
8 intuition or "gut feeling" since they are not in touch with their emotions properly, thus, are not
9 affected by the FE as much, as this is an emotionally induced bias.

10 On the other hand, **interoception** is one's ability to detect and process subtle internal
11 bodily sensations (e.g. hunger, thirst, changes in respiration or cardiac signals, etc.) triggered
12 by external stimuli related to an emotional experience. Studies show that higher level of
13 interoception is related to higher intensity of emotional awareness and more detailed
14 emotional processing (Herbert, Herbert, & Pollatos, 2011; Pollatos, Herbert, Matthias, &
15 Schandry, 2007). Moreover, it has also been linked to better decision-making. For instance,
16 studies with decision-making under risk have shown that participants' interoceptive abilities
17 affect their performance in these tasks (Bechara, Damasio, Tranel, & Damasio, 1997; Dunn et
18 al., 2010; Sütterlin, Schulz, Stumpf, Pauli, & Vögele, 2013). It is believed that interoception
19 affects decision-making by increasing our subjective emotional experience triggered by our
20 bodily responses to external stimuli (Barrett, Quigley, Bliss-Moreau, & Aronson, 2012;
21 Critchley, Wiens, Rotshtein, Öhman, & Dolan, 2004; Wiens, Mezzacappa, & Katkin, 2000;
22 Zaki, Davis, & Ochsner, 2012). Even though the studies linking interoception and the FE are
23 scarce, some research has been done to give us few clues. Sütterlin et al. (2013) and Shah et
24 al. (2016) in their studies concluded that high interoception was positively correlated with a
25 higher susceptibility to the FE. It makes sense, as we described above, the FE has emotional

1 bases, therefore accurate emotional processing can determine its level of influence on the
2 decisions by triggering somatic responses in the individual and making them more prone to be
3 affected by this bias.

4 Although the relationship between alexithymia or interoception and the FE has been
5 studied separately, to our knowledge, it has not been explored to date how both constructs
6 interact and influence decision-making, more specifically, the FE in healthy people. This
7 possible relationship has been tested in the clinical settings. For instance, recently, Palser et
8 al. (2018) concluded that a high level of alexithymia could be a risk factor for anxiety, but
9 especially in people with a high level of interoception. However, in the case of having poor
10 interoception, having more or less alexithymia did not seem so relevant. Thus, it seems that
11 having more or less alexithymia becomes especially relevant *only* when the individual is
12 already aware of the interoceptive signals coming from the body. Therefore, returning to
13 decision-making, it makes sense that a greater alexithymia explains a lower FE, but especially
14 in people who have a good interoception level and, as we propose, this occurs because the
15 interoceptive signals are misattributed to emotions due to the presence of alexithymia.
16 However, first the person must be able to detect those signals; perhaps that is why alexithymia
17 is less important in people who have poor interoception.

18 Taking this into account, the aim of this study is to explore these relationships and how
19 these variables interact with each other to influence decision-making under risk. As we
20 mentioned above, data on the relationship between the moderating role of high or low ability
21 of emotions detection and regulation, measured in interoception and alexithymia, and the
22 susceptibility to the FE is scarce, our study is intended to dig into this question and provide
23 more scientific evidence of the directionality of the possible relationships. Firstly, we
24 hypothesize (**hypothesis 1**) that participants would choose to accept the bet (take more risk)
25 under the negative frames more than the positive ones, in other words, they would show more

1 FE. Secondly, we expect that interoception would positively and alexithymia would
2 negatively predict the FE (**hypothesis 2**), since higher emotional awareness would facilitate
3 the emotional feedback loop leading to a more intuitive decision-making and inability to do
4 that would hinder the process. Finally, we predict that (**hypothesis 3**) the interaction between
5 interoception and alexithymia would have a significant effect and interoception would
6 moderate the relationship between alexithymia and the FE, in a way that depending on the
7 levels of interoception, alexithymia would play more or less relevant role in this process. It
8 would happen because first one needs to be aware of owns bodily changes, it means having
9 high interoception, and *only* then, whether the person is able to regulate and attribute these
10 sensations to emotions effectively or not (level of alexithymia) would be significant.

11

12 **2. METHOD**

13 **2.1. Participants**

14 Based on the effect size found in a previous work on the FE and alexithymia (Shah et al.,
15 2016), an a priori power analysis using G*Power (Erdfelder, Faul, & Buchner, 1996)
16 indicated a requisite of 33 participants ($\eta^2_p = .44$, power = 80%, $\alpha = .05$) to perform a general
17 lineal model studying interoception, alexithymia and their interaction to predict the FE. We
18 oversampled 10 participants to account for possible exclusions. 43 healthy participants were
19 recruited by the mean of non-probabilistic sampling method, from which one was eliminated
20 due to a physical disability and for not having been able to perform the framing task well on
21 the computer. Hence, the final number of participants was 42, (women: N = 27; age: M =
22 22.50, SD = 2.734). All of them fulfilled the exclusion criteria as follow: not having physical,
23 neurological or psychiatric diseases; not consuming 10 or more cigarettes a day; not
24 consuming drugs on regular bases; not having consumed drugs 24h before and not having
25 taken stimulant drinks in the 2h before the experimental session; sleep deprivation and BMI.

1 The study was approved by the Ethics Research Committee of the University of
2 Valencia in accordance with the ethical standards of the 1969 Declaration of Helsinki. All
3 participants signed informed consent before starting the experimental session and were
4 informed about which activities they had to perform and which equipment was going to be
5 used (electrodes to measure electrocardiogram, ECG, for instance), also insisting on that they
6 were free to withdrawal their consent at any point of the study.

7 **2.2. Instruments**

8 2.2.1 Framing task

9 *Risky-choice framing task*

10 Participants completed a computerized version economical risky-choice framing task
11 adapted from De Martino et al. (2006). First of all, a screen appeared for 2 seconds informing
12 them that they received an amount of money (€25, €50, €75 and €100). Next, a screen with
13 two options appeared simultaneously for 4 s, where they were asked to choose between a
14 “sure” option and a “risky” option. The reason behind the time constraining was to enhance
15 the effects of implicit information processing, as proposed by the original authors.

16 On the one hand, the “sure” option could be presented either in a negative frame (e.g.
17 “You lose €75”) or in a positive frame (“You keep €25”). Point to be noticed, the actual
18 monetary value is equal in both options and the only difference is how they are worded. On
19 the other hand, the “risky” option consisted of gambling to either win or lose the whole
20 amount of money announced before. The probabilities to win the risky option were 20%,
21 40%, 60% and 80%; and the trials were equally balanced between these probabilities, it
22 means, same number of trials for each percentage of riskiness. Types of frame, positive or
23 negative, were randomly presented; however, the number of trials for each type of frame was
24 equal (32 loss and 32 gain frames). In addition, the “risky” option in a specific positively

1 framed trial was equivalent to its complementary negative frame's "risky" option. It means,
2 for every positive trial (e.g. "You keep €60 of €100" vs. a 60% chance of keeping the whole
3 €100), there was a complementary negative trial (e.g. "You lose €40 of €100" vs. 60% chance
4 of keeping the whole €100). As you can see, "risky" option remains the same, but "sure"
5 option changes depending on how it is framed (a visual representation of two complementary
6 framed trials is represented in the figure 1).

7 Following the protocol from the original authors, participants were not given any
8 feedback if they lost or won the gamble, in order to avoid a possible decisions shift because of
9 the context dependence of risk preferences (Tversky & Kahneman, 1992; Vermeer & Sanfey,
10 2015; Xue, Lu, Levin, & Bechara, 2011). For example, studies have shown that participants
11 prefer risky options after a financial loss, while choosing safer options after a monetary gain.
12 Another important reason was that each trial was intended to be a unique bet and a trial-by-
13 trial feedback could promote learning by reward/punishment-based conditioning, which could
14 result in adapting a strategy to gain more money (Bechara et al., 1994; Chiu, Huang, Duann,
15 & Lin, 2018; Turnbull, Bowman, Shanker, & Davies, 2014). This feedback based learning
16 could introduce bias to our data since the purpose of our study was to measure risk-taking in
17 each independent bet under different contexts (frames).

18 In addition 32 "catch" trials were included; where one of the alternatives was notably
19 beneficial in comparison to the other one (e.g. 95% chances to win/lose the whole amount vs.
20 keeping/losing 50% of the initial amount). These were to assess the participant's engagement
21 and to assure that the answers were not random. Following the design developed by De
22 Martino et al., (2006), any participant failing in more than 20% of these "catch" trials were
23 excluded from the study.

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2 Figure 1. Risky-choice framing task. Two complementary trials are presented. First a screen with a “+” symbol
 3 appears for 3 seconds in order to prepare the participant for the trial. Second, participants receive an initial
 4 amount (2 seconds). Third slide appears (for 4 seconds only) with a “sure” (on the left) and a “risky” option
 5 (green being the probability to win and red the probability to loss all the initial amount). The “sure” option can
 6 either be framed as a gain (“keep”) or as a loss (“loss”). Types of frame, positive or negative, were randomly
 7 presented; however, the number of trials for each type of frame was equal (32 loss and 32 gain frames). No
 8 feedback was given if the bet resulted in a win or a loss.

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10 2.2.2. Interoception

11 We used the *Schandry heartbeat tracking task* (Dunn et al., 2010; Schandry, 1981). This
 12 task is divided into six trials. In each trial, the participants have to count how many heartbeats
 13 they felt during changing time of intervals - two trials of 25s; two of 35s and last two ones of
 14 40s - without being permitted to take their pulse. Afterwards, these results are compared with
 15 their real heartbeats they had during those intervals measured by the ECG. Heartbeats were
 16 recorded using the third Einthoven derivation with 3 re-usable electrodes, using BIOPAC
 17 MP150, a transducer ECG-100C and the AcqKnowledge 4.2.0 software.

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1 2.2.3. Alexithymia

2 We used the *Toronto Alexithymia Scale* (TAS-20; Bagby, Parker, & Taylor, 1994). It is
3 the most extensively used self-report to measure alexithymia construct. It consists of 20 items,
4 and participants must answer the questions in 5-point Likert scale, where “1” means
5 “completely disagree” and “5” means “completely agree”. The score can range from 20 to
6 100, with higher score indicating a high level of alexithymia (a score higher than 71 indicates
7 clinical-level alexithymia diagnosis).

8 We used the Spanish version of TAS-20 (Martínez-sánchez, 1996); Cronbach’s alpha for
9 our sample was .63.

10 2.3. Procedure

11 Participants who showed interest in participating in the study were asked to provide us
12 their contact information (email and mobile number) and the day and time they preferred for
13 the session. Through an online questionnaire, all the participants provided information about
14 their socioeconomic variables, as well as their physical and psychological health. In addition,
15 we asked them about their lifestyle style (psychostimulant drug uses, drug addiction, physical
16 activity, etc.). In this same questionnaire TAS-20 was included to measure alexithymia. The
17 reason behind to add the questionnaire here was to avoid any influence that the framing task
18 could have on their emotional expression. Participants were instructed to wait in the faculty
19 hall and were guided to the lab by the main researcher in the elevator avoiding the stairs to
20 avoid any fluctuations in their physical or physiological states (fatigue or increasing
21 heartbeat). Once in the lab, they all signed informed consent and were informed about the
22 study and equipment used, without revealing the exact purpose and variables of the study.
23 Next, to measure ECG, electrodes were attached to their body and they were left alone for 10
24 minutes to take a baseline. After this habituation phase, they performed the heartbeat tracking

1 task to assess interoception, which was followed by the Risky-choice framing task with a 5
2 minutes rest in between. Instructions for this task were printed on a paper with visual
3 examples for a better comprehension. Participants also performed few test trials in order to
4 grasp the task well before really starting.

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6 **2.4. Data reduction**

7 2.4.1. Risky choice framing task

8 First, to guarantee a sufficient internal validity, any participant who failed more than
9 20% of “catch” trials was excluded from the further analysis. In addition, it was assured that
10 the positioning of the frames (right vs left) did not have a significant influence on the
11 decisions. Finally, the FE was measured by calculating the difference between the preference
12 (in percentage) to choose the “gamble” option over the “sure” option within each frame. In
13 other words, the difference between the percentages of trials the individual chose to gamble in
14 a positive frame versus a negative frame.

15 2.4.2. Schandry Heartbeat Task

16 The participants’ performance on this task was measured by using the following
17 formula: $((Actual - Estimated) \div Actual) \times 100$, where “Actual” is the heartbeats the
18 participant really had at that interval of time as estimated by ECG and “Estimated” are the
19 number of heartbeats participants felt they had, it means, the answer they gave. These results
20 are presented in the percentage form. We calculated the percentages for the six trials and
21 computed the average. The scores can be interpreted as a continuous scale, where higher
22 scores mean better interoception.

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1 2.5. Statistics analysis

2 First step was to check outliers and test variables normality with Kolmogorov-Smirnov
3 normality test. Variables that did not follow normal distribution were converted using the
4 Ig10 conversion method. First, we tested for the FE through a repeated-measures ANOVA,
5 comparing risk taking in positive vs negative frames. After that, we did a two stepped
6 analysis, as previously mentioned. First, to study if interoception, alexithymia and their
7 interaction predicted the FE, we carried out a general linear model. Once the significant
8 interaction was assured, we followed the Johnson-Neyman procedure with the PROCESS
9 macro for SPSS (Hayes, 2017). Johnson-Neyman method identifies important transition or
10 critical points (JN) where the effect of the moderator variable (in this case, interoception), on
11 Y (effect of alexithymia on the FE), transitions from significant to nonsignificant, or vice
12 versa (see Montoya (2019) for a detailed explanation).

13 All analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics 25, with the α significance level
14 set at .05.

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1 3. RESULTS

2 3.1. Descriptive statistics

3 In the table 1, descriptive characteristics of our variable of interest are presented.

Table 1. *Descriptive statistics (N = 42)*

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Framing effect	.21	.17
Bet acceptance under positive frame	.28	.19
Bet acceptance under negative frames	.49	.22
Interoception trial 1	65.95	17.42
Interoception trial 2	66.27	18.71
Interoception trial 3	64.42	22.61
Interoception trial 4	63.78	21.49
Interoception trial 5	62.70	19.36
Interoception trial 6	63.38	20.61
Final interoception	63.93	16.47
Alexithymia	40.52	7.12

4 M = mean; SD = standard deviation; framing effect score, is measured by calculating the difference between the
5 proportion of trials the participant chose to gamble in the positive frames versus at the negative frames; final
6 interoception score (in percentage) is calculated by averaging the interoceptive precision (also in percentages) in
7 6 heartbeat tracking trials; alexithymia (ranging between 20 – 100), sum 20 items of TAS-20.

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10 3.2. Framing effect

11 First, we checked if any participant failed more than 20% of the “catch” trials. In our
12 case, no participant was excluded for this reason. Secondly, we discarded the possibility that
13 the positioning of the frames (right vs left) could be affecting participants’ choices by
14 conducting a mean comparison ($M = .2068$, $SD = .1845$ and $M = .2068$, $SD = .1875$,
15 respectively) and no significant differences were observed, $F(1, 41) = .00$, $p = 1.00$. After
16 assuring the internal reliability with these two steps, we got into our specific hypotheses
17 testing.

18 As far as our first hypothesis is concerned, participants indeed tended to take more risk
19 (accepting to bet) in loss frames than in gain frames ($M = .4896$, $SD = .2227$ and $M = .2827$,
20 $SD = .1955$, respectively), $F(1, 41) = 169.083$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .805$.

1 3.2. Alexithymia and interoception

2 Only as a verification that there is no correlation between alexithymia and interoception
3 so that the following analysis can be done well, we ran Pearson correlation between them,
4 which resulted not significant ($r(42) = -.031; p = .845$). Then, once having assured the
5 independence of these two variables, using a general linear model to see how interoception,
6 alexithymia and their interaction predicted the FE, we observed that there were significant
7 main effects of interoception ($B = .019, SE = .008, t = 2.34, p = .024, \eta^2p = .12$), and
8 alexithymia ($B = -.128, SE = .048, t = -2.68, p = .01, \eta^2p = .15$). It means both constructs are
9 significant predictors of the performance in the FE task, interoception being positively and
10 alexithymia negatively correlated with the FE. In addition, we found a significant
11 Interoception*Alexithymia interaction ($B = -.013, SE = .005, t = -2.64, p = .01, \eta^2p = .15$),
12 indicating that interoception moderates the effects of alexithymia on the FE. The model was
13 significant, $F(3, 38) = 3.35, p = .02$, and explained the 20.9% of the FE's variance. In order to
14 deepen even more in this interaction, the Johnson-Neyman procedure was followed, which
15 revealed that having a punctuation of 59.45 in interoception was a critical point (see Figure 2).
16 Scores lower than this point did not show significant associations between alexithymia and
17 the FE, contrary to those who scored higher, which showed a negative association between
18 alexithymia and the FE.

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2 **Figure 2 – Johnson-Neyman graph.** Graph of the conditional association between alexithymia and the Framing
 3 effect, as a linear function of Interoception including the Johnson–Neyman transition point (*JN*). The *JN* point is
 4 where the confidence interval around the condition effect intersects zero on the y-axis. Thus, the shaded quadrant
 5 is the region of significance, i.e. those vaules of interoception for which the association between alexithymia and
 6 the framing effect was significant.

7

8 4. DISCUSSION

9 In the present study we aimed to study how the FE, a cognitive bias, may be influenced
 10 by alexithymia and interoception. Not much research has been done exploring these variables
 11 under the same experiment design and the main objective of our study was to dig into these
 12 relationships and provide more evidence on this topic. We hypothesized that people would be
 13 more conservative when encountering positively framed alternatives and more risk-taking
 14 with negatively framed alternatives, i.e., they would show a framing effect (Tversky &
 15 Kahneman, 1981). In addition, these differences in preferences would be negatively and
 16 positively associated with alexithymia (Shah et al., 2016) and interoception (Sütterlin et al.,
 17 2013), respectively. It would happen because this cognitive bias is routed in our emotional
 18 system (De Martino et al., 2006; Ring, 2015; Roiser et al., 2009; Sarlo et al., 2013) and an

1 inability or ease to detect, process and regulate our bodily sensations and emotions would
2 affect this. Going even further, we suggested that interoception would moderate the
3 relationship between alexithymia and the FE. Our results seem to support these hypotheses
4 and show that interoception and alexithymia indeed play a significant role in the decision-
5 making involving the FE.

6 The main result from our study is that alexithymia only predicted low FE in those
7 individuals who displayed a high interoception. It means: a good level of body awareness
8 (high interoception) was a necessary condition for alexithymia to have a significant effect on
9 our decisions. In order to explain that, we propose that this happens because of a two
10 independent stages process: when encountered with an emotional stimulus (a bet in our case),
11 our body sends us signals via somatic responses (SCRs, heartbeat change, sweating...), which
12 an individual can become aware of or not depending in their interoception level (level 1). If
13 there is a defect in this level, it means, if one is not aware of the signals sent by their bodies, it
14 does not matter how and how well we label these signals (level 2). Put in another way,
15 alexithymia, which is attributing somatic responses to emotions, would have an effect on our
16 decisions *only* when these signals become conscious by functional interoceptive ability,
17 hinting that they conduct on two different levels (Palser et al., 2018). These two levels are
18 independent and a deficiency in one does not mean a defect in the other one necessarily. In
19 fact, different studies have showed that interoception and alexithymia are independent
20 constructs (Bird, Press, & Richardson, 2011; Marchesi, Brusamonti, & Maggini, 2000; Palser
21 et al., 2018), as also backed by our correlational results. Thus, we can assume that they are
22 two independent aspects that must coincide for a person to be more aware of their emotional
23 responses.

24 These results can be explained by the **somatic marker hypothesis** (Bechara & Damasio,
25 2005; Poppa & Bechara, 2017) which takes into account how emotions derived from external

1 stimuli affect our decision-making process. It assumes, contrary to the assumption that human
2 decision-making is fully rational and systematic, that emotions play a determining role in
3 decision-making. It posits that when encountered with a decision, different stimuli trigger
4 somatic states (changes in heartbeat, SCRs, sweating, respiration changes, etc.) and depending
5 on either these states are considered positive or negative by the individual, the behavioral
6 outcome will be affected (Bechara & Damasio, 2005; Finucane, Alhakami, Slovic, &
7 Johnson, 2000; Slovic, Finucane, Peters, & Macgregor, 2004).

8 Taking the above description into account, just like we described before, it is a two-phase
9 process: the first phase is the production and awareness of the somatic states triggered by a
10 stimulus and *only* when these changes come into our awareness, the way we attribute them,
11 correctly or not, to different emotions (second phase) will have an impact on our decisions.
12 The first phase is dependent on our interoceptive abilities while the second one is subject to
13 how effectively we recognize these changes and “label” them as different emotions; it means
14 the level of alexithymia. However, for alexithymia to have a significant influence on our
15 decisions, we first must be aware of the sensations coming from our body, if not, it means
16 little, just like backed by our results.

17 Our findings can have important implications for decision-making and decision-making
18 dysfunctions that have been reported in many psychiatric disorders resulting in excessive risk-
19 taking or impulsivity in some disorders (e.g. Dom, Sabbe, Hulstijn, & Van Den Brink, 2005;
20 Moeller et al., 2001; Swann et al., 2005) or excessive risk-aversion or demotivation in others
21 (e.g. Epstein, 2006). These patients could benefit from the intervention programs involving
22 interoception and emotional regulation training since it is been shown that decision-making
23 process is highly influenced by somatic states awareness and emotional integration,
24 promoting an adaptive decision-making in addition to a better learning of advantageous
25 decision-making strategies (Bechara et al., 1997; Chiu et al., 2018; Dunn et al., 2010; Kano,

1 Ito, & Fukudo, 2011). In line with the somatic marker hypothesis (explained above), this
2 occurs because decision-making is a complex process, which is constantly influenced by the
3 feedback coming from the outside and from our own body. Hence, a good understanding of
4 own body reactions in certain situations and correct attribution and regulation of emotions
5 can ease this feedback system in order to promote more responsible decisions avoiding
6 excessive risk-taking or risk-aversion.

7 All in all, interoception accuracy and emotional regulation and expression training, such
8 as with biofeedback or mindfulness, can promote a better acceptance and communication of
9 own bodily feelings and self-control of the physiological processes (e.g. Nanke & Rief, 2004)
10 and like this contributing to a more conscious decision-making.

11 Despite the interesting results, our study is not exempt from limitations. One of the main
12 limitations is the sociodemographic homogeneity of our sample. Majority of our participants
13 were young middle class healthy university students making the generalization of our results
14 difficult to people of different ages and with different socioeconomic statuses. Another
15 limitation is the use of the experimental financial paradigm and not real-life decision-making.
16 In the future it would be interesting to contrast these results with real-life dilemmas since
17 research has showed preference differences depending on what we are playing with (human
18 lives vs money or objects) (Rönnlund, Karlsson, Lagnäs, Larsson, & Lindström, 2005).
19 Another thing to consider in the future is that we only measured interoceptive accuracy, how
20 well one is *objectively* able to detect bodily sensation, in our case, counting heartbeats. In
21 future research interoceptive sensibility, *subjective* perception of how accurate one is in
22 perceiving bodily states, would be desirable since previous studies have showed mixed results
23 regarding its relationship with alexithymia (Herbert et al., 2011; Shah et al., 2016). Finally,
24 we would like to highlight that our reliability index for the alexithymia was quite low (.63)
25 and in future studies a higher reliability would be desirable.

1 Studies coping with the question how alexithymia and interoception, separately and
2 combined, affect the FE are rare and our research provides another evidence of the
3 relationships between these variables, which is in accordance with the previous results.
4 However, our study, to our knowledge, is the first to link the interaction between alexithymia
5 and interoception to the FE and provide the evidence that there might be a two-stage
6 processing of the emotional decision-making.

7

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